

A Trustworthy Framework for Multi-Cloud Service Management: Self-Sovereign Identity Integration

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Abstract—Self-Sovereign-Identity (SSI) technologies based on blockchain networks (BCNs) are increasingly used in various industries, including telecommunications. To address the strict governance of telecommunication infrastructure, we propose a decentralized architecture based on BCN and BCN-based SSI for network management and orchestration to fully involve multiple entities in the management. The proposed solution aims to provide a trusted environment for Cloud Service Providers (CSPs), Vertical Service Providers (SPs) and Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) to manage the lifecycle of network services (such as instantiation, scaling, termination) in a multi-cloud environment. The identity authentication mechanism ensures control of permissions and cross-entity collaboration. The proposed approach is validated through an experimental scenario using Hyperledger Indy and Quorum BCN to measure various performance metrics related to service orchestrator (SO)-related instantiation and SSI credential verification metrics to ensure improved feasibility, scalability, reliability, and performance. Our evaluation results show that the average time for writing data to the BCN is on the order of seconds, while the average times for different credential operations range from milliseconds to several hundred milliseconds, indicating that these operations are accomplished within shorter timeframes in the implemented system. We also provide recommendations for optimizing the system and address some observed challenges.

Index Terms—blockchain, self-sovereign identify, service orchestration, vertical services, network management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Advanced technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI)/Machine Learning (ML), blockchain, Network Function Virtualization (NFV) and Software-Defined Networking (SDN) are implemented by Cloud Service Providers (CSPs) and Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) to facilitate on-demand access to a shared resource pool of networks, computing power, storage, applications and services. These technologies enable secure, reliable, and cost-effective development and management of network and cloud services. However, the diverse requirements for network services and a range of application needs require collaboration between different players in the cloud and telecommunications systems

sector. The main players in this space must collaborate, each specializing in distinct segments such as computing, systems, networks, and applications. This collaborative approach requires cross-domain collaboration between cloud and telecom providers to effectively address the growing complexity of managing and orchestrating services.

Blockchain Network (BCN) technology has recently become an important tool for improving the security and visibility of network management and orchestration systems in multi-cloud environments [1], [2]. The decentralization, immutability, trust mode, and smart contract programming features of BCN can offer innovative solutions for the network service Lifecycle Management (LCM) process when multiple parties are involved. For this reason, telecommunication companies are pursuing the development of common blockchain-enabled platforms to seamlessly integrate with their network management frameworks and methodologies to improve the efficiency and reliability of network services. In this way, the telecommunications industry can create new use cases and derive greater benefit from this innovative technology. By integrating blockchain into their infrastructure, the telecommunications industry aims to achieve fast and efficient network services characterized by high scalability and security in various network lifecycle management operations such as instantiation, termination and scaling. Several research studies [3], [4] underline the need for blockchain-based solutions in the telecommunications sector.

In this paper, we use BCN-based Self Sovereign Identity (SSI) and BCN to create a trusted environment for LCM of network services in a multi-cloud environment. The overall goal is to improve the governance and control of network service LCM, transparency, and access management using authenticated identities when network service provisioning is required between multiple CSPs and MNOs.

II. BACKGROUND, RELATED WORK AND CONTRIBUTIONS

A. Decentralized Trust and BCN-based SSI

BCNs, as highlighted in [5]–[10], have found extensive application in ensuring cyber-security for the Internet of Things (IoT), Internet of Vehicles (IoV), data auditing, and Edge-Fog computing domains under multi-cloud or multi-tenant scenarios. Decentralized identifiers (DIDs) and Verifiable Credentials (VCs) are key components of SSI systems based on blockchain technology.

DIDs function as distinctive identifiers linked to entities or individuals within a decentralized identity system, serving

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This work was partially funded by MCIN/AEI/ 10.13039/501100011033 “ERDF A way of making Europe” project under grant PID2021-126431OB-I00 and Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO)—Program UNICO I+D (grants TSI-063000-2021-54 and -55).

merely as pseudonyms. VCs contain a set of claims issued by an entity regarding a subject, which can undergo cryptographic verification. DIDs and VCs help ensure the authenticity of both issuers and holders within a SSI system. Blockchain technology serves as an enabler of SSI by providing a decentralized and secure infrastructure for managing digital identities and can be used as a DID and VC register. By implementing a Distributed Identity Management (DIM) system, accountability and traceability can be improved. DIM system allows tracking of the use, ownership, and interactions of specific equipment, entities, or inventory objects through unique DIDs. This ensures that services are exclusively delivered by authorized providers and facilitates efficient resource management. For example, associating a DID with the Management and Network Orchestration (MANO) platform enables its unique identification within the SSI system, enabling the MANO platform to utilize satellite services while excluding fixed communication networks. DIM systems can also provide features such as accountability through digital signatures (e.g., to enable smooth operation of network services LCM process that contributes to the accountability and non-repudiation aspects), data privacy and user consent (e.g., entities involved in the network LCM process must consent to the sharing of their credentials and data, and this consent is cryptographically validated, thus preserving the privacy and integrity of the system) and improved auditability (e.g., every network LCM operation, interaction, credential exchange, and resource allocation are logged in an immutable ledger to ensure that the system can be audited for compliance, accountability, and transparency).

When considering the deployment of BCNs in mobile network environments, performance becomes a critical factor in selecting the most appropriate blockchain scheme. Metrics such as latency and Transactions per Second (TPS) play an important role in evaluating performance [11]. Several leading companies and groups, including IOTA¹, Dfinity², Ethereum³, Lightning Group⁴, and NEO⁵, are actively engaged in pioneering blockchain 3.0 projects [12]. At the same time, there are many blockchain frameworks/research projects that support user-centric digital identity. *EBSI (European Blockchain Services Infrastructure)*⁶ is an initiative by the European Commission to provide a trusted and secure infrastructure for digital services across Europe. It includes a focus on digital identity and aims to enable SSI through blockchain technology. *ID Union* is an open-source project that focuses on decentralized digital identity solutions⁷. It aims to provide a framework for building interoperable and privacy-preserving identity management systems using blockchain technology and promotes SSI principles and standards. *Hyperledger Indy* is a blockchain framework specifically designed for decentralized identity. It provides a set of reusable components and

libraries that enable the creation of SSI systems. Hyperledger Indy incorporates features such as verifiable credentials, zero-knowledge proofs, privacy-preserving attribute exchange, and DID management. *SSI IOTA* is an implementation of self-sovereign identity on the IOTA Tangle, which is a Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) that does not use traditional blockchain. It leverages IOTA's infrastructure to enable secure and decentralized identity management. *ConsenSys* is a blockchain software technology company that offers various solutions and frameworks for decentralized identity. One of their notable projects is uPort, which is built on the Ethereum blockchain and provides self-sovereign identity capabilities. On the other hand, despite the existence of successful BCN solutions, experimental evaluations and their overall impact on evolving telecommunication network architectures and specific use case requirements have not been sufficiently explored in the existing literature, especially for multi-stakeholder scenarios where BCN and BCN-based SSI technologies may be used in network services LCM.

B. Network Service Lifecycle Management

The utilization of BCNs and BCN-based SSI provides an opportunity to establish a trusted environment among entities involved in network service provisioning across multiple administrative domains [13] and among a restricted group of untrusted entities [14]. In the context of 5G mobile networks operating in multi-cloud environments, collaboration between MNOs, CSPs, and vertical Service Providers (SPs) is necessary for effective service orchestration and management. For example, in a multi-domain edge computing service deployment scenario, multiple organisations may collaborate to deploy edge computing services in different geographic regions. The collaboration may involve setting up a network service that leverages edge computing resources to efficiently deliver services. These different organizations can also collaborate to manage and optimize network services that span different geographic regions to ensure efficient and reliable delivery of network services while continuously monitoring and adapting to changing conditions. However, given the competitive nature of CSPs, creating a trustworthy environment between MNOs and CSPs becomes crucial. Providing a corporate identity within an SSI framework enables the secure representation and management of an organization's identity. This enables vertical SPs, operators, and CSPs to establish their legitimacy and credentials within the network, ensure trust, and facilitate secure interactions with the MANO stack for network services LCM process. By embedding authorization capabilities, secure provisioning and management of services can be ensured, regardless of the access method (fixed, mobile, or satellite). Access restrictions or blocking can be implemented based on the associated ID and granted authorizations. In addition, in the event of service delivery failures or problems, the SSI system can help identify the responsible party by using the unique DIDs associated with the entities involved.

To ensure accountability, authenticity, and transparency, service managers and requesters must first identify CSPs failing to meet agreed Service-Level Agreement (SLA) requirements,

¹Online: <https://www.iota.org/>, Available: May 2022

²Online: <https://dfinity.org/>, Available: May 2022

³Online: <https://ethereum.org/en/>, Available: May 2022

⁴Online: <https://lightning.engineering/>, Available: May 2022

⁵Online: <https://neo.org/>, Available: May 2022

⁶Online: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/european-blockchain-services-infrastructure>, Available: May 2023.

⁷Online: <https://github.com/IDunion>, Available: July 2023.

and ensure transparency between entities to prevent dishonesty and blame-shifting for network service failures [15]. A novel framework is proposed in [16] that leverages dynamic trust evaluation to enhance access control mechanisms and ensure security in multi-cloud environments. In a different study [17], researchers analyze the geographical distribution characteristics of data centers for multi-cloud operations, employing a clustering algorithm and proposing a cost-effective data initialization strategy. While [18] presents a hierarchical routing system that incorporates dynamic SLA management to optimize Quality-of-Service (QoS), Li et al. [19] explores mechanisms for scaling services at different levels (application, service, and resource) by leveraging the hierarchical SLA management framework. In [20], the network is scaled to overcome throughput challenges in blockchain consensus. The proposed framework utilizes subnets organized hierarchically, enabling on-demand creation and different consensus algorithms, increasing network capacity and benefiting from parent subnets' security through periodic state checkpointing. Furthermore, the authors of [21] demonstrate the feasibility of multi-domain solutions utilizing the 5Growth (5Gr) (*5G-enabled Growth in Vertical Industries*)⁸-MANO, enabling diverse stakeholders to engage at various levels. However, in a multi-domain environment, the process of service instantiation is dynamic and necessitates collaborative efforts among multiple entities. This process should be swift and transparent to all involved parties, including vertical SPs and MNOs.

C. Our Contributions

Evaluating the convergence of BCN-based SSI with network management and orchestration tools on a small scale will be a critical first step toward a larger real-world service deployment with proper network management and orchestration while building trust among stakeholders. The main objective of proposed BCN and BCN-based SSI architecture in this paper is to enhance the transparency and efficiency of network management and orchestration processes, bypassing lengthy authentication and contractual procedures between multiple CSPs and MNOs when network service provisioning is required. The key contributions of this paper are as follows: **(i)** An innovative decentralized architecture for multi-stakeholder environment is introduced for mobile network management and orchestration, leveraging blockchain technology. **(ii)** A comprehensive architecture, incorporating various functionalities and interfaces, that integrates a BCN and BCN-enabled SSI into the 5Gr-Service Orchestrator (SO) platform is developed. We focus on a network management and orchestration system that involves several types of entities, including CSPs, MNO, vertical SPs, responsible ministries, legal authorities, and regulatory bodies. **(iii)** Our scheme is realized through the utilization of a permissioned Quorum and Hyperledger Indy BCNs. In term of the network service instantiation times achieved, it is observed that the average time for writing data to the BCN is on the order of seconds, whereas the average times for different credential operations range from milliseconds to

Fig. 1: Network service request of a vertical in a multi-cloud environment.

several hundred milliseconds, indicating that these operations take less time in the implemented system.

The structure of the paper is as follows: Section III presents the overarching system and introduces the entities participating in the permissioned blockchain-based service orchestration. The design of the BCN-based SSI Application Programming Interface (API) and the workflow of the proposed scheme for MANO operations are discussed in Section IV. The experimental testbed details and results are presented in Section V. Section VI analyzes the evaluation findings and discusses the challenges associated with implementing the proposed architecture. Lastly, Section VII offers conclusions drawn from the study.

III. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

In this section, we present a novel framework for network service management and orchestration in a multi-cloud environment, utilizing a BCN-based distributed access control and authentication mechanisms. Fig. 1 provides a visual representation of the authentication and LCM of BCN-based network services for verticals in a multi-cloud environment. The platform receives and processes network service requests according to associated identities and permissions in the BCN-based SSI system, ensuring effective governance and control over resource and service access. When a network service request is made, CSPs and MNOs can verify their identities through BCN-based SSI and record the number of network resources they can provision or currently have available in the BCN. Each operational step in managing and orchestrating the network service is recorded as a separate transaction in the BCN's blocks. This approach simplifies the identification of responsible parties in case of any issues during network service management. The proposed framework comprises the following essential elements: **(i)** All entities involved are authenticated to 5Gr-MANO stack, which enables autonomous decision-making for end-to-end NFV-Network Service (NS) composition and decomposition across multiple administrative domains, via BCN-based SSI. **(ii)** The 5Gr-MANO stack ensures that the requirements of NFV-NS are fulfilled and facilitates the aggregation of virtual resources and services from various providers through their respective SOs. **(iii)**

⁸<https://5growth.eu/>, Available: January-2022

The BCN ensures trust and transparency within the multi-cloud network service management environment. It provides a secure and decentralized platform for managing and verifying network service transactions, enhancing the overall reliability and accountability. (iv) The architecture incorporates multiple CSPs and SPs, including mobile and cloud infrastructure providers, as well as vertical SPs. These entities contribute to the overall ecosystem by offering their respective resources, services, and expertise to support the delivery of network services in a multi-cloud environment.

In short, the integration of BCN-based SSI strengthens the 5Gr-MANO system by creating decentralized trust, improving ownership and control of data, enhancing security through cryptography, creating an immutable audit trail, facilitating efficient credential exchange, promoting interoperability, and reducing dependence on central authorities. Together, these features contribute to a more secure, transparent and flexible ecosystem for managing and orchestrating network services.

A. System Components and Actors

Fig. 2 shows the entities involved in the authentication, approval, transaction, and block commit processes for network service LCM using permissioned BCN-based network service orchestration and management with multiple entities in a multi-cloud environment. Within this framework, the deployment of a BCN-based network service relies on the collaboration of multiple entities, including vertical SPs, CSPs, MNO (which owns 5Gr-MANO, the legal authority, the responsible ministry, and the regulator, who must work together and establish clear roles and responsibilities for the implementation of a BCN-based service orchestration architecture and controls. In our proposed system, each participating entity is expected to function as a full blockchain node, undertaking security-related operations, committing transactions to the ledger, and contributing to the consensus process. The roles of each participant depicted in Figure 2 are described as follows:

MNOs: act as the owner of the MANO stack and BCNs. They also engage in interactions with regulatory authorities and vertical SPs. **Issuer:** They are able to issue an authorization card to a holder that allows access and use of the MANO stack. The issuer can be legal authority, responsible ministry or regulation authority in corresponding country. **CSPs:** must have identifiers in the system (DIDs controlled by their owners) and have connectivity to invoke and read access decisions made by verifiers, i.e., MANO stack. In our proposed system, the primary responsibility of the CSPs is to provide the necessary infrastructure for network service provisioning. They engage in collaboration with MNOs to jointly deploy network services. **Vertical SP:** engage in interactions with the 5Gr-MANO stack, specifically requesting a customized network slice that aligns with their specific service requirements. Once the request is made to the issuer to use MANO stack owner, the credential is created for the vertical SP which is entitled to make network service requests as long as the credential is valid. **5Gr-MANO stack:** is the verifier in our use case. The smart contract is associated with a specific MANO stack (one or more) and is tasked with verifying the credentials presented

Fig. 2: Authentication, approval, transaction and block-commit phases and their connectivity relationships.

by the holders (vertical SP in the upper layer and CSPs and MNOs in the lower layer interactions). Access is granted according to the access policies defined in the smart contract, which are compared to the content of the presented VCs. **SSi infrastructure:** The Hyperledger Indy blockchain platform is used as the identity layer for our system, is the access management component and acts as the authorization layer for our system. This requires that a running Hyperledger Indy blockchain is managed by different entities (to ensure decentralisation). **BCN infrastructure:** The log transactions related vertical CSPs, MNOs and CSPs accessing MANO, the time of access, operational steps etc. are periodically written to on-chain BCN component by interaction with HyperLedger BCN and is implemented with Quorum BCN. Hence, it used by the decentralized authorization application as the blockchain backend to interact. The **Responsible Ministry** serves as an approver in the process, representing the local authority responsible for endorsing the specific network service. The **Legal Authority** also serves as an approver in the process, responsible for ensuring compliance with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) for the requested network service. The **Regulation Authority** is the national telecommunications regulatory and functions as an independent administrative entity responsible for overseeing, regulating, and supervising the telecommunications sector.

Note that the performance of a network management and orchestration system can be affected by the number of entities involved in the process. However, modern network management and orchestration solutions are also designed for scalability. This can be achieved by using a distributed network management architecture (see, for example, [22]) or by using cloud computing. To accommodate a growing

network ecosystem, advances in cloud computing and DLTs have also given us the tools we need to manage increasing complexity.

B. Main Phases

First, in the initial state of the process in *approval phase* of Fig. 2, all entities involved are authenticated via BCN-based SSI. Later, the approvers, represented by the responsible ministry and legal authority in our example, play a key role in endorsing the request to instantiate the network service. The second step of the process involves the vertical SP submitting an approval request to the relevant bodies, such as the responsible ministry and legal authority. During the *approval phase*, the vertical SP seeks the endorsement of these authorities before proceeding with the instantiation of the network service. Let's consider an example where the vertical SP operates in the agriculture sector. In this scenario, the ministry of agriculture is informed of the intention to establish a new IoT network service in the field. The purpose of this notification could be to undergo safety and efficacy testing for the IoT devices used in network services for agriculture before they are deployed in the field. Additionally, the ministry reviews the request in compliance with the regulations to determine whether the IoT device can be utilized for the proposed service. Subsequently, based on these considerations, the responsible ministry either approves or denies the request. Following the approval phase, the network service is instantiated by the 5Gr-MANO (owned by MNO) with the supervision of the BCN during the *transaction phase*. In this phase, both service related operations of vertical SP and CSP are converted into transactions. Subsequently, the 5Gr-MANO engages in negotiations with the regulators through the BCN during the *block commit phase*. Once the negotiation process is successfully completed, the network service can be securely instantiated. In an operational network service system, BCN ensures secure, authenticated and transparent utilization of network services and entities defined above. The entity responsible for the network service (in this case, the MNO) utilizes the BCN and BCN-based SSI to authenticate, track and manage all the operational steps involved in the network service management process and address any deployment and authentication issues that may arise among multiple entities. The network service should only be instantiated once it satisfies all the requirements.

C. Authentication Entities

The proposed decentralized and trustless system empowers entities involved in network service LCM process with greater control over their enterprise data while enabling secure and verifiable digital interactions. Fig. 3 shows an overview of the actors involved in BCN-based SSI. There are five key entities: the issuer, the holder, the verifier, the SSI BCN and (online) BCN. **1-) The issuer (e.g. a regulation authority in charge of vertical service in each country)** is an entity that is authorized to create and issue digital credentials or verifiable credentials to individuals or entities. These credentials contain certain claims or attributes about the holder. The issuer typically generates the credentials as digital objects and signs them

using their private key, thus ensuring their authenticity and tamper resistance. The signed credentials are then stored in a way that preserves their integrity and authenticity. **2-) The holder** is an entity (e.g., vertical SPs, CSPs) who receives and possesses the digital credentials issued by the issuer. The holder has control over their own credentials and can choose when and how to present them to verifiers. The credentials are stored in the holder's digital wallet or enterprise data store, which is usually secured using cryptography and protected by the holder's private key. The holder can selectively share specific credentials or attributes with verifiers based on their needs or requirements, thereby exercising control over their own data. **3-) The verifier (5Gr-MANO in our case)** is an entity that needs to verify certain claims or attributes about an entity. When a verifier needs to verify the authenticity or validity of a claim made by a holder, they can request the presentation of specific credentials or attributes relevant to their verification process. The verifier relies on the cryptographic signatures and integrity of the credentials to trust their authenticity. By verifying the digital signatures and the integrity of the credentials using the issuer's public key, the verifier can ensure that the credentials were indeed issued by a trusted issuer and have not been tampered with. **4-) SSI BCN (e.g., HyperLedger Indy)** serves as the underlying blockchain network that supports the SSI system. The SSI BCN plays a crucial role in maintaining the distributed ledger of credentials, public keys, and transaction history, providing a trustless and decentralized infrastructure for the SSI system. **5-) Online BCN (e.g., Quorum)** is another separate BCN that is involved in the interactions for log transactions.

Quorum and Hyperledger Indy are both permissioned blockchain networks, which means that only authorized participants can join the network providing security and privacy for network management and orchestration. Additionally, they offer a number of other advantages, such as *(i) Scalability within context*: Both of them are designed for scalability within context, meaning they can be used to support large numbers of participants and transactions using techniques such as sharding, sidechains, or consortium networks. These approaches can be tailored to meet the specific scalability requirements of the system without sacrificing privacy and control. *(ii) Flexibility*: Both are flexible platforms that can be customized to meet specific application requirements. *(iii) Interoperability*: Both are interoperable with other blockchain platforms, so they can be used to connect different systems and applications. Note that while public blockchains have their advantages, such as scalability, the decision to use a private blockchain (both Quorum and Hyperledger Indy) in the proposed architecture was made for a number of reasons, including for cost reasons (lower resource requirements for operations), for privacy and control reasons (they provide a higher level of privacy and control and are therefore suitable for applications that involve sensitive or confidential information), and for regulatory compliance reasons (to ensure regulatory compliance by controlling access to data and ensuring that only authorized participants are part of the network).

Fig. 3: Overview of the authentication process with BCN-based SSI and actors involved in the process and system workflow. There exist five main entities: the issuer, the holder, the verifier, the SSI blockchain network, and the (online) blockchain network.

D. The Authentication Process

The steps and interactions in the process are as follows: **(i) Registration and DID Creation:** All participating entities (issuers, holders (service providers), 5Gr-MANO stack, smart IoT devices of vertical SPs) are registered in BCN-based SSI (e.g., Hyperledger Indy in our analysis) and provided with a DID. All interactions between entities are set up with a DID authentication to authenticate each other and exchange credentials or authorization requests, as shown in step-1 and step-2 of Fig. 3. **(ii) Smart Contract Publication:** The issuer is responsible for publishing smart contract(s), either one smart contract for each 5Gr-MANO stack or one smart contract for a group of 5Gr-MANO stacks. The 5Gr-MANO stack is configured to contact (at least) one smart contract. It may also happen that owners of 5Gr-MANO stack (i.e., MNOs) cooperate to jointly publish a smart contract. Note that if the 5Gr-MANO stack owner chooses to use an existing smart contract developed by another party, services (in the form of smart contracts) can be offered by other companies. This creates an open market for smart contract development, as they can generate fees to reward developers. **(iii) Holder Requests Access:** The 5Gr-MANO stack is configured to contact at least one smart contract for authorization decisions. When a holder (in our case can be vertical SPs, MNOs or CSPs depending on how they want to interact with 5Gr-MANO) wants to access the service, an interaction with the issuer occurs via Hyperledger Indy, and an authenticated channel is established (**step-1** in Fig. 3). **(iv) Credential Issuance:** The issuer can then issue a verifiable credential to the requesting holder (**step 2**), including specific terms for the smart contract and the 5Gr-MANO stack to refine access policies for that specific holder, i.e., authorized time slots, a specific part of 5Gr-MANO stack, etc. **(v) Credential Presentation:** In **step 3** of Fig. 3, the holder presents the credentials to the 5Gr-MANO stack (verifier) when requesting access to the service. **(vi) Credential Verification:** The 5Gr-MANO stack forwards the pre-

sented credentials to the Hyperledger Indy. The 5Gr-MANO stack verifies ownership, authorship, and non-revocation of the credential (**step 4**). The verifier also checks the credential against a list of access policies – as the credential contains claims – set by the issuer. Note that the smart contract on Hyperledger Indy has exclusive invocation properties that are limited to the issuer and the 5Gr-MANO stack(s) controlled by that smart contract. **(vii) Failure Handling:** If authentication fails, the 5Gr-MANO stack stops instantiating service requests from vertical SP or does not cooperate with CSPs or MNOs that are not authenticated. **(viii) Smart Contract Invocation:** If the authentication and credential verification succeed, the 5Gr-MANO stack is authorized to invoke the smart contract on the separate BCN (Quorum) to access policies related to 5Gr-MANO stack operation. As shown in **step 5** of Fig. 3, the BCN-based SSI invokes smart contract on online BCN for 5Gr-MANO access policies with the presented credentials. **(ix) Online BCN 5Gr-MANO Interaction:** The 5Gr-MANO stack is informed by the smart contract about the authorization to write in BCN (**step-6** of Fig. 3). **(x) Network Service Instantiation:** After authentication succeeds, the 5Gr-MANO stack starts network service instantiation in collaboration with MNOs and CSPs, and logs are written to the BCN (Quorum in our case).

IV. BLOCKCHAIN API DESIGN & WORKFLOW

The proposed architecture, depicted in Fig. 4, outlines the integration of BCN and BCN-based SSI with various modules such as Vertical Slicer (VS), SO, Resource Layer (RL), and Vertical Oriented monitoring system (VoMS) in the 5Gr-MANO stack [21]. Within this stack, the mentioned modules follow the architectural foundations proposed by ETSI NFV-MAN 001, communicating each other by means of a REST API based on the HTTP protocol and JSON language for message encoding. This communication aligns with the procedures defined mainly in ETSI NFV IFA 013, IFA 005, IFA 030 specifications for the network service lifecycle management and the information models described in ETSI NFV IFA 014, 011 to package network service and virtual network function descriptors. It is worth mentioning that some extension has been implemented on the mentioned procedures to support extended functionality, e.g., SO-SO federation [23]. These modules are effectively managed and controlled through their interaction with BCN and BCN-based SSI. At the top layer of the 5Gr stack, 5Gr-VS handles Network Slice Requests (NSRs) originating from vertical providers. NSR is a request to create a network slice. NSRs are submitted by vertical service providers to a MANO system. 5Gr-SO offers network service orchestration and resource orchestration capabilities, enabling the instantiation of network slices within and across multiple domains. 5Gr-RL takes charge of managing network and infrastructure resources, including routers, switches, and servers. Meanwhile, VoMS serves as a platform for collecting, storing, and processing operational information based on received metrics from deployed services. It collaborates with VS, SO, or RL to gather operational steps related to network service and management. Instantiating network slices within

Fig. 4: 5Gr-MANO architectural stack integrated with BCN-based SSI and BCN.

domains and across domains can be done in a number of ways. A common approach is to use a centralized MANO system (e.g. 5Gr-MANO), which is used in this paper due to the small number of domains. In this approach, the 5Gr-MANO system is responsible for managing all aspects of the network slice lifecycle, including instantiation, configuration, and decommissioning. The instantiation of network slices across multiple domains is coordinated by a federated 5Gr-MANO stack.

A. Interactions with BCN

The detailed service management and orchestration with the BCN sequence diagram between BCN and SSI entities is presented in Fig. 5. This sequence diagram showcases the interactions and flow of information between the involved entities in the BCN for network service management and orchestration. The sequence of events is as follows: (i) The vertical SP initiates by checking the availability of resources. (ii) Next, 5Gr-MANO verifies the availability of resources across the distributed ledger using smart contracts. (iii) If the resources are available, the vertical SP sends a network service request for instantiation, scaling, or termination. (iv) 5Gr-MANO validates the credentials via BCN-based SSI, creates a transaction for network management and orchestration operations, configures the necessary parameters, and submits the transactions to the smart contract. (v) 5Gr-MANO subscribes to the "write-finish event," which is triggered after all operational steps are successfully written to the distributed ledger. 5Gr-MANO receives a corresponding message indicating the success of the instantiation steps. (vi) Once the network service lifecycle management request is confirmed, 5Gr-MANO sends a confirmation message to the vertical SP regarding the successful instantiation of the service. Note that the process in the

sequence diagram in Fig. 5 does involve a distributed ledger system, but specifically uses blockchain technology, smart contracts, and SSI to achieve management and orchestration of network services, which distinguishes it from a general distributed ledger system. Blockchain technology and smart contracts provide additional functionality and capabilities that are not inherently part of all distributed ledger systems.

B. BCN SSI API

The BCN-based SSI integration in the 5Gr-MANO stack simplifies the process of enabling SSI capabilities across various components such as VS, SO, RL, and VoMS. This eliminates the need for separate interfaces for each component when utilizing blockchain operations. The 5Gr-MANO architecture is built upon the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) NFV architecture and specifications. The BCN-based SSI handles identity management while other entities are collaborating to instantiate network services.

The integration of the 5Gr-MANO stack with the BCN-based SSI is facilitated through the BCN SSI API, which is accessed by each layer of the 5Gr stack. The corresponding API and its associated URIs are depicted in Fig. 6. The BCN API functions as an application and is connected to various resources, each identified by specific identifiers. These resources include the Committer, Approvers, Transactions, and Authentication. To initiate a transaction, the vertical service provider sends a request to the transaction URI, which is managed by the BCN API through the 5Gr-VoMS component. The Transaction resource can be accessed using the GET function. Prior to interacting with the BCN API, an authentication process is performed. The transaction identifiers and ID numbers are stored in the transaction representation and utilized by the Transaction resource. Subsequently, the POST

Fig. 5: A sequence diagram demonstrating the service management and orchestration with a BCN.

request is made for the Approvers. If the Approvers reach a consensus, the Committer resource is invoked to write the transaction data to the blockchain block. BCN API details can be found in our previous related work in [2].

C. Workflow of the Proposed Scheme

The BCN-enabled MANO process involves several steps. Initially, all entities are verified using access control mechanism of BCN-based SSI to verify credentials to ensure identity protection. Then, CSPs and MNO collaborate to create a whitelist of agreed and offered NFV-NS, forming a service catalog. The vertical SP sends a request for NFV-NS instantiation to the 5Gr stack’s VS, which translates it into 5Gr-SO. The Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator (NFVO) of 5Gr-SO decomposes the requested NFV-NS, and a decision is made to consume one of the nested NFV-NS through federation. Then, resource availability information is checked in the Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure (NFVI) repository of the 5Gr-SO and stored in the BCN. The NFV-NS catalog is checked to find a potential provider from another administrative domain. The availability of the requested service is checked by sending requests to the potential providers. Feedback on availability is received, and based on the responses, the MNO’s 5Gr-SO selects the CSP’s 5Gr-SO for NFV-NS instantiation or terminates the procedure if no positive responses are obtained. Collected data and contracts

Fig. 6: BCN-SSI API unified modeling language diagram.

are stored in the credential record database. Parameters for 5Gr-MANO are set, and transactions for approval are created and sent. Smart contracts are activated in the BCN, and blocks are created by interacting with nodes. The commit block is executed by the regulator authority’s node, and logging service instantiation requests are sent to the BCN from 5Gr-MANO. Real-time monitoring data is ingested, and the consensus model confirms transactions. Results of the logging service instantiation steps are returned by the BCN to 5Gr-MANO. Finally, the selected CSP’s 5Gr-SO updates its catalog database, and positive feedback is sent upon the successful instantiation of the requested federated NFV-NS. This workflow can also be expanded to accommodate various other network service and management activities, including scaling or termination, and can be applied to different layers of the 5Gr-MANO stack, such as VS and RL.

V. EXPERIMENTAL IMPLEMENTATIONS & RESULTS

A. Test Setup for DIM and SO

In our test setup, the OpenStack platform is used. Two virtual machines are created in OpenStack. A Representational State Transfer (REST) server is created to generate the appropriate requests to Hyperledger Indy. One of the virtual machines has a REST API. The other virtual machine has a DID system set up in a container-based structure. Hyperledger Indy is used for the DID blockchain as an identity layer for the test setup. A total of 8 GB RAM, 4 vCPUs, and 40 GB of disk space are reserved for the DID virtual machine in Openstack. During the Hyperledger Indy installation, the von network setup⁹ was performed on which container-based nodes will run. A total of four DID container nodes were

⁹VON Network, Available: <https://github.com/bcgov/von-network>, Online: March 2023.

TABLE I
BLOCKCHAIN NETWORK SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT

Host OS	Windows 10 Pro (V21H1)
Guest OS	Ubuntu 20.04.3 LTS on Vmware Pro (2 Cores on VM)
Docker Containers (Under Full Load)	Node1: CPU: 30% Memory Usage: 640 MB
	Node2: CPU: 9% Memory Usage: 371 MB
	Node3: CPU: 11% Memory Usage: 375 MB
CPU	AMD Ryzen 5 Pro 3400G 3.70 Ghz (2 Cores assigned to VM)
Memory	16 GB 2666MHz DDR4 (6 GB assigned to VM)

created as DID issuers. A REST API is used to send requests from users to BCN. REST API is implemented using Flask framework. Calls to the BCN were made by implementing the DIDComm messaging protocol (an asynchronous encrypted communication protocol developed as part of the Hyperledger Aries project¹⁰).

In experimental evaluations, we consider the "Connected Worker: Augmented Zero Defect Manufacturing (ZDM) Decision Support System (DSS)" use case described in [24]. We use an Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV) as the instantiated service. Operational and management logs are collected during service instantiation. The AGV is mobile, has its own Customer Premises Equipment (CPE), and moves near the Coordinate Measuring Machine (CMM) to identify the code of manufactured pieces as they come off the production line. The log file is collected by the 5Gr-VoMS layer through the Mo-BCN interface, as depicted in Fig. 4 of our architecture. The log file is then transmitted to the BCN, which consists of three nodes, using a JavaScript app. JavaScript application reads the file line by line and sends each line as transactions. The simulation environment details are presented in Table I. During the simulations, all transactions are sent from the external user to Node 1. As the other nodes only update their own databases, their memory and central processing unit (CPU) consumption are lower compared to Node 1.

In our evaluation of the BCN, we use several metrics to compare results. These include the *block size (measured in bytes)* of the Quorum BCN, *TPS*, *time to write* to the BCN (which includes verification time and network latency), and the number of transactions. Typically, in our evaluations, we send one transaction for each row in the logs. However, in certain scenarios, we also vary the number of log lines sent for each transaction. This allows us to examine different transaction configurations and their impact on BCN performance. To ensure compatibility with the BCN, we prepare the logs in such a way that they can be made available to the network per operation. This means that the logs are isolated based on specific operations, which allows for more detailed analysis and evaluation. In addition, we include a log called "total instantiation time" that encompasses all other logs and provides an aggregate measure of the entire process. To ensure the reli-

ability and robustness of our results, we conduct experiments with 10 replicates during our evaluations for both network service instantiation and blockchain performance comparisons where standard deviations of results did not indicate significant variability that would compromise the reliability of results in experiments.

B. Credential and SO Specific Metrics

Credential Metrics: We begin with REST API for registration of users (credential offer) and for verification of registered user (credential presentation). In addition, we calculated the average connection establishment times and the average signing times of messages for the DIDComm protocol. Table II provides the averages of experimental DID implementation for credential operations after REST API calls to five endpoints for communication with DID blockchain system. The *average credential presentation time* measures the average amount of time it takes for verification process to transpire, covering the time between the user presents the credential to the verifier and the verifier completes the verification. This read operation is represented by third and fourth steps in Fig. 3. The *average credential offer time* measures the average amount of time it takes for an issuer to generate and offer a credential in response to a user's request. This includes the time it takes for the issuer to authenticate the user and check the validity of their request, as well as the time it takes to generate the credential and share it with the user. This write operation is represented by first and second steps in Fig. 3.

Average DIDcomm connection creation time measures the amount of time it takes for two parties to establish a secure communication channel using the DIDcomm protocol. This includes the time it takes for each party to authenticate the other party's identity, exchange DIDs and credentials, and negotiate the cryptographic parameters necessary for secure communication. According to our numerical results, this process takes the longest time in comparison to other metric time values. The *average DIDcomm connection signing time* measures the average amount of time it takes for two parties to sign a DIDcomm connection using digital signatures. This includes the time it takes for each party to verify the other party's identity, generate and sign the necessary cryptographic keys, and negotiate the cryptographic parameters necessary for secure communication. Note that *Average DIDcomm connection creation time* and *average DIDcomm connection signing time* are necessary for any transactions to be on BCN. In other words, DIDcomm must be established first to compute metrics such as *average DIDcomm revoke credential time*, *average credential presentation time* and *average DIDcomm revoke credential time* values.

The *average DIDcomm revoke credential time* measures the average amount of time it takes for an issuer to revoke a verifiable credential and notify the relevant parties using the DIDcomm protocol. This includes the time it takes for the issuer to identify the need for revocation, generate and sign the revocation credential, and notify the relevant parties through a secure communication channel. This operation executes write and is represented by first step in Fig. 3. Note that revocation can only be executed by the issuer.

¹⁰Aries RFC 0005: DID Communication, Available: <https://bit.ly/3TKFUKG>, Online: March 2023.

SO-specific metric: In our evaluations, we use the 5Gr-SO specific metric called *Total instantiation time*. It measures the time elapsed from service identifier generation to full instantiation of the network service.

C. Credentials Results

As shown in Table II, all Key Parameter Indicators (KPIs) described above are measured for three different scenarios with 50K, 75K, and 100K requests. In general, the results of the experiment indicate that as the number of requests increases, the performance of the DID management system degrades. However, the amount of increase in the number of requests is not directly proportional to increase in the average time values observed in KPIs. When comparing the average credential offer time across the three scenarios, we can observe an increase of 14.29% (from 525 milliseconds to 603 milliseconds) as the number of requests doubles (increases from 50K to 100K). The increase in average credential presentation time is even more pronounced, with a percentage increase of 18.18% (from 33 milliseconds to 39 milliseconds) between 50K and 100K requests. The average DIDcomm connection creation time and DIDcomm connection signing time also exhibit an increasing trend as the number of requests increases. The average DIDcomm connection creation time increases by 11.7% (from 659 milliseconds to 736 milliseconds) and the average DIDcomm connection signing time increases by 12.5% (from 64 milliseconds to 72 milliseconds) between 50K and 100K requests. The average revoke credential time for 50K requests is 212 milliseconds, while the average revoke credential time for 100K requests is 277 milliseconds, which represents an increase of 30.66%. Note that the percentage increase in revoke credential time gets higher with additional requests. This suggests that the performance of the system in handling revocation requests may be more affected by the number of requests than other operations such as credential presentation, offer, and DIDcomm connection creation and signing. Factors such as network latency and system hardware and software may also play a role. As the number of requests increases, the network becomes more congested, which can slow down communication between the various nodes. Furthermore, if the system is not powerful enough, it may not be able to handle the load of processing so many requests.

D. Network Service Instantiation and Blockchain Results

Our primary objective is to measure the time required for writing different logs related to the instantiation of 5Gr-SO within the BCN. Table III provides the average and standard deviation values of experimental metrics for network service instantiation using total instantiation logs using Quorum BCN. The metrics used are the average time it takes to complete the instantiation process, the total number of log lines recorded during the instantiation process, the average number of blocks involved in the instantiation process, the average delay experienced in the network during the instantiation process, the average number of transactions processed per second during the instantiation process and the average time taken to write data during the instantiation process. These metrics provide

TABLE II
AVERAGE AND STANDARD DEVIATION VALUES OF EXPERIMENTAL DID IMPLEMENTATION FOR CREDENTIAL OPERATIONS.

KPI	50K Requests	75K Requests	100K Requests
Average credential presentation time (msec)	33 \pm 1.63	35 \pm 1.25	39 \pm 0.82
Average credential offer time (msec)	525 \pm 2.45	565 \pm 1.63	603 \pm 0.81
Average DIDcomm connection creation time (msec)	659 \pm 1.24	681 \pm 2.90	736 \pm 1.63
Average DIDcomm signing time (msec)	64 \pm 1.42	68 \pm 1.94	72 \pm 0.82
Average DIDcomm revoke credential time (msec)	212 \pm 2.13	256 \pm 1.42	277 \pm 3.62

TABLE III
AVERAGE AND STANDARD DEVIATION VALUES OF EXPERIMENTAL METRICS FOR NETWORK SERVICE INSTANTIATION USING TOTAL INSTANTIATION LOG IN QUORUM BCN.

KPI	Value
Average time to instantiate (s)	120.1705 \pm 0.23
No. of log lines	1724
Average no. of blocks	475 \pm 21.15
Average network delay (ms)	0.047 \pm 0.004
Average TPS	63 \pm 5.90
Average time to write (s)	27.226 \pm 3.93

insights into the performance and efficiency of the network service instantiation process. The average time to instantiate, number of log lines, and network delay metrics indicate the time-sensitive nature of the process. The average number of blocks and average TPS metrics provide information about the scalability and transaction processing capability of the system. The average time to write metric reflects the efficiency of data storing on BCN operations during instantiation.

VI. DISCUSSIONS, CHALLENGES & FUTURE DIRECTIONS

It is observed that the average time for writing data to the BCN is on the order of seconds, which provides insight into the duration required for this process. At the same time, the average time to instantiate the network service will also depend on a number of factors, including the specific application, the expected performance requirements, the type of requests. For example, some network requests may be more complex than others (which may require composite network services) and may take longer to process. In general, a lower average time is generally better because it means that the system responds more quickly. However, there may be cases where a higher average time is also acceptable, e.g., if the application is not time-critical. The average times for different credential operations range from milliseconds to several hundred milliseconds, indicating that these operations take less time in the implemented system as given in Table II. Thus, the experimental scenario shows that the credential operations can only slightly increase the duration of the network service instantiation process compared to the case where no BCN-based SSI is used. Specifically, the average time for network service instantiation is approximately 120.1705 seconds, while

the average time for credential operations, which includes credential presentation, offer, DIDcomm connection creation, signing, and credential revocation, ranges from 33 to 736 milliseconds, depending on the specific operation and number of requests. To put this into perspective, the credential operations add less than 0.61% to the total time of network service instantiation. This minimal impact on the instantiation process highlights the efficiency and practicality of our approach, especially considering the significant security and trust benefits offered by the BCN-based SSI framework. By comparing observed metrics, it is possible to identify potential areas for optimization and improvement in the network service instantiation process. For example, if the average time to instantiate is high compared to the desired target, optimization strategies can be explored to streamline the process and reduce deployment time. Similarly, if the average network delay is significant, optimizing network infrastructure or communication protocols can help enhance performance. Note that optimizing the use of blockchain technology is a proactive approach to improving system performance. Careful consideration of consensus mechanisms, scalability solutions, smart contract optimization, interoperability, efficient resource allocation, data management, caching, and regular maintenance can help make the system more efficient and responsive. Considering the potentially long lifespan of network services, it becomes valuable to record the instantiation operations in a BCN. This enables all entities within the BCN to verify and access these operations, promoting transparency and accountability throughout the network. In addition, adopting a more efficient blockchain implementation can significantly reduce costs in the system. Careful consideration of transaction fees, resource utilization, scalability solutions, smart contract efficiency, data management, monitoring, governance, interoperability, use of open source tools, use of cloud services, and regular audits can significantly improve the overall cost efficiency of the system.

While BCN-based SSI for authentication and BCN for log tracking offers several benefits, such as increased privacy, confidentiality, data integrity and user control, there are also some associated challenges that need to be addressed. Some of these challenges include: **(i) Trust over the issuers:** In an SSI ecosystem, multiple issuers generate and issue verifiable credentials. Establishing trust in these issuers becomes crucial, as individuals need to rely on the credibility and accuracy of the credentials which requires robust verification mechanisms and reputation systems. **(ii) Challenging process of certifying issuers:** Certifying issuers in an SSI ecosystem can be complex. There is a need for a reliable and standardized process to assess the credibility, security practices, and data protection measures implemented by issuers. Developing such certification processes can be time-consuming and resource-intensive. **(iii) Trust over the presenter of VCs:** It is crucial to ensure that the person presenting the VC is the rightful owner and that their private key has not been compromised. Techniques like multi-factor authentication and cryptographic mechanisms can help mitigate this risk. **(iv) Regulatory framework ambiguity on using DLT and smart contracts:** DLT and smart contracts form the backbone of many SSI implementations. However, there can be regulatory ambiguities

and uncertainties regarding the legal validity and enforceability of transactions executed on these technologies. Developing clear legal frameworks that address these concerns is essential to foster wider adoption of SSI. **(v) Data tampering attacks:** The performance of the BCN API can be compromised under high data rates, which can lead to compromised data. Although transactions written to the block in BCN are unaffected by data loss, there is a risk of transaction loss during the confirmation process and interrupted queues due to network delays in dynamic environments. To address these challenges, integrating a sequence number into transactions alongside transaction timestamps can provide additional assurance of data integrity. **(vi) Collusion** between CSPs and MNO can pose challenges in meeting the requirements of vertical SPs, potentially leading to unfair prioritization of larger SPs over smaller ones. To address this issue, a secure processing system can be introduced as an additional layer to establish trust. One solution is to have a pre-established business agreement where CSPs declare the resources they can dynamically provide, recorded as transactions on the BCN. Updates can be recorded whenever a new service is instantiated to indicate the remaining available resources which promotes fair resource allocation and prevents discrimination against smaller vertical SPs. **(vii) Security threats:** By integrating BCN with an AI/ML platform, timely notifications can be generated to network service providers, allowing for proactive detection of incoming attacks such as Denial of Service (DoS) or intrusion attacks. This proactive approach enhances the overall security posture and helps mitigate the impact of such attacks. **(viii) Credential revocation and service termination:** The process of terminating network services or revoking credentials can pose challenges, especially when certain components of the services are interconnected. These components may be utilized by multiple services, making their proper functioning crucial. Therefore, it is essential to establish synchronization mechanisms to ensure proper coordination between services and their interconnected components during the revocation or termination process. **(ix) Dynamicity:** Selecting the most suitable BCN for dynamic environments involves considering factors such as low latency, high transaction throughput (TPS), and scalability. However, meeting all these requirements can be challenging, particularly in unsynchronized networks like those found in IoT environments. **(x) Business Intents:** It is important to understand to fulfill NSRs from verticals that lack specific technical details but contain business-oriented information. A converter structure, such as an intent layer [25], can be used to bridge the gap between business requirements and infrastructure components. Finally, note that addressing these challenges requires collaboration above between stakeholders, including technology providers, regulatory bodies, and industry consortia. Efforts should be made to establish standardization, certification, and legal frameworks to ensure the security, privacy, and trustworthiness of SSI ecosystems.

Some future prospects to explore are as follow: **(i) Enhanced Scalability** To address scalability challenges, future prospects should include exploring techniques such as sharding, off-chain processing, sidechains, or Layer 2 scaling solutions such as Lightning Network or Optimistic Rollups.

(ii) Reduced Resource Footprint: Continued advances in hardware and software technologies can lead to more efficient cryptographic operations and reduced resource requirements. Future optimizations should aim to make the solution more resource efficient so that it can run on a wider range of hardware configurations. **(iii) Interoperability:** The development of interoperability protocols and standards, such as blockchain bridges and cross-chain atomic swaps, can facilitate the seamless transfer of data and assets between blockchains. Interoperability with other SSI frameworks and identity ecosystems should also be considered. **(iv) Security and Privacy:** Future developments should further advance encryption methods, zero-knowledge proofs, and privacy-preserving smart contracts to strengthen security and privacy policies.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a BCN-based framework for network service management and orchestration including authentication with BCN-based SSI, allowing multiple stakeholders to efficiently handle network service lifecycles. By leveraging smart contracts and treating the blockchain as a trusted network, the framework ensures security and transparency in delivering network services. The proposed solution supports network service orchestration across multiple clouds, involving various CSPs and MNO. Evaluation results indicate significant variations in service instantiation time and blockchain metrics, suggesting diverse transaction loads and speeds. Additionally, extensive simulations were conducted to calculate average values for KPIs in a DID management system, providing insights into credential operations and associated error codes encountered during the simulations. The paper also discusses challenges and offers recommendations based on the evaluation findings.

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